

PRELIMINARY ANALYSIS AND DESIGN STUDY OF SHIP HULL CROSS SECTION USING A HIGH-ORDER SANDWICH THEORY APPROACH

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ABSTRACT

Results obtained as part of a preliminary design study regarding a composite sandwich ship hull cross section is presented. The modeling and analysis is conducted using a high-order sandwich theory formulation in which the elastic response of each face laminate is accounted for, including bending-stretching coupling, and including the transverse flexibility of the core material. The paper includes a presentation of the high-order sandwich theory approach adopted for the analysis, including the formulations for flat and curved sandwich panels, respectively. The paper is concluded by the presentation of numerical results obtained for a model composite sandwich hull cross section subjected to hydraulic head loading as well as the static equivalent of underwater "blast" loading.

INTRODUCTION

Structural sandwich panels can be considered as a special type of composite laminate where two thin, stiff, strong and relatively dense face sheets are separated by a thick, lightweight and compliant core material. Such sandwich structures have gained widespread acceptance as an excellent way to obtain extremely lightweight components and structures with very high bending stiffness, high strength and high buckling resistance [1-2]. Among the applications where sandwich materials and structures are being used successfully, spacecraft and aircraft structures, ship hulls and ship superstructures, high-speed trains, wind turbine blades, cargo containers and tanks for trucks can be mentioned.

As mentioned, ship hulls and ship superstructures are already being manufactured as composite sandwich structures, where especially the Royal Swedish and Royal Danish Navies have accumulated vast experience through the successful application of all sandwich naval vessels over the last thirty years. However, the understanding of the mechanics of sandwich structures is still less than satisfactory on a number of points. Among these, the following can be mentioned: Load introductions and joints, localized bending effects in the vicinity of material and geometrical discontinuities, interaction and compatibility with adjoining structures, which may be sandwich panels, composite laminates or metallic structural components. Localized shearing and bending effects are induced at the mentioned locations, and will induce severe shear and through-thickness normal stresses that may approach or even exceed the allowable stresses in the faces, the core material or in the interfaces between the core and the faces.

Figure 1. Schematic illustration of composite sandwich ship hull cross section subjected to hydraulic head and underwater blast loads.

The paper presents the results of a preliminary analysis and design study of an idealized composite sandwich ship hull cross section, as shown schematically in Fig. 1. The sandwich ship hull cross section (hereinafter referred to as the CS) is comprised of straight and curved sandwich panels, and the typical load conditions consist of hydraulic head and slamming loads, occasionally accompanied by aerial and underwater blast loads. These loads induce a complex stress state in the sandwich hull CS. The presented study is simplified in that only a 2-D plane stress or plane strain model of a hull CS is considered, in that symmetry is assumed about the vertical mid-plane, and in that the deck of the hull is dismissed in the analysis. Thus, only the side of the hull CS is considered under simple and approximate boundary conditions: 1) The upper part of the side is assumed to be clamped (“deck” condition), and 2.) “Equivalent vertical symmetry” conditions are assumed at the “keel”.

The objective of the study is to quantify the characteristics of the structural response. Emphasis is focused on describing the complicated interaction between the faces through the core material in the vicinity of points where the geometry changes, and in the vicinity of points where restrictive boundary conditions are imposed (“deck” and “keel”).

STRUCTURAL MODELING

The design study is performed using a high-order sandwich theory formulation in which the elastic responses of the face laminates are accounted for individually, including bending-stretching coupling, and in which the transverse core flexibility is included. Thus, the model allows the panel thickness to change during deformation, and the model accounts for the existence of both shear and transverse normal stresses in the core material. The adopted model is equivalent to the high-order sandwich formulations introduced for the analysis of flat sandwich panels by Frostig et al. [3-7], for the analysis of adhesive joints by Frostig, Thomsen and Mortensen [8], and for the analysis of curved sandwich panels by Frostig [9] and Bozhevolnaya and Frostig [10]. More recently, the formulation was adopted by Thomsen for the analysis of multi-layer plate

$$\begin{aligned}
\tau_c(x, z) &= \tau_c(x), \quad \sigma_c(x, z) = \frac{E_c}{c} \{w_1 - w_2\} - \tau_{c,x} z \\
w_c(x, z) &= w_1 + \frac{w_1 - w_2}{c} \left\{ z - \frac{c}{2} \right\} - \frac{\tau_{c,x}}{2E_c} \left\{ z^2 - \frac{c^2}{4} \right\} \\
u_c(x, z) &= u_{01} + \frac{w_{1,x}}{2} \left\{ f_1 - \frac{z^2}{c} - z + \frac{3c}{4} \right\} + \frac{w_{2,x}}{2} \left\{ \frac{z^2}{c_i} - z + \frac{c}{4} \right\} \\
&\quad + \frac{\tau_c}{G_c} \left\{ z - \frac{c}{2} \right\} + \frac{\tau_{c,xx}}{2E_c} \left\{ \frac{z^3}{3} - \frac{c^2 z}{4} + \frac{c^3}{12} \right\}
\end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

CURVED SANDWICH PANELS

$$\begin{aligned}
\tau_c(r, \theta) &= \frac{\tau(\theta)}{r^2}, \quad \sigma_c(r, \theta) = \frac{\tau(\theta)_{,\theta}}{r} \left\{ \frac{1}{r} - \lambda_1 \right\} + \frac{\{w_1 - w_2\}}{r} \lambda_2 \\
w_c(r, \theta) &= w_1 + \frac{1}{E_c} \left\{ (w_1 - w_2) \lambda_2 \ln(r/R_c^t) - \tau(\theta)_{,\theta} \left\langle \frac{1}{r} - \frac{1}{R_c^t} + \lambda_1 \ln(r/R_c^t) \right\rangle \right\} \\
u_c(r, \theta) &= \frac{r}{R_c^t} \left\{ u_{01} - \frac{f_1}{2} \beta_1 \right\} - \frac{\tau(\theta)}{2G_c} \frac{(R_c^t)^2 - r^2}{r(R_c^t)^2} + w_{1,\theta} \frac{R_c^t - r}{R_c^t} + \frac{\tau(\theta)_{,\theta\theta}}{E_c} \left\langle \frac{R_c^t - r}{(R_c^t)^2} \right. \\
&\quad \left. - \frac{(R_c^t)^2 - r^2}{2r(R_c^t)^2} - \lambda_1 \left[\frac{R_c^t - r}{R_c^t} + \ln(r/R_c^t) \right] \right\rangle + \frac{(w_{1,\theta} - w_{1,\theta})}{\ln(R_c^t/R_c^b)} \left\langle \frac{R_c^t - r}{R_c^t} + \ln(r/R_c^t) \right\rangle \\
\lambda_1 &= (R_c^t - R_c^b)/R_c^t R_c^b \ln(R_c^t/R_c^b), \quad \lambda_2 = E_c / \ln(R_c^t/R_c^b)
\end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

For flat sandwich panels it is seen from Eqs. (1) that \square_c is predicted to be constant, that \square_c varies linearly, that w_c varies quadratically, and finally u_c varies cubically across the core thickness. For curved sandwich panels Eqs. (2) show that all core quantities vary non-linearly across the core thickness.

Face equations and the complete set of governing equations

In accordance with the approximate 2-D analysis presented herein, the faces of the hull section are modeled as laminated beams with bending-stretching coupling. The modeling is based on the Euler-Bernoulli assumptions, i.e. the transverse shear deformations in the faces are ignored.

Thus, the constitutive relations for the faces read:

$$N_i = A_{11}^i \varepsilon_{0i} + B_{11}^i \kappa_i, \quad M_i = B_{11}^i \varepsilon_{0i} + D_{11}^i \kappa_i, \quad i = 1, 2 \tag{3}$$

where N_i, M_i are the normal stress and bending moment resultants, \square_{0i}, \square_i are the normal strain and the curvature change of the face sheet mid-line, and $A_{11}^i, B_{11}^i, D_{11}^i$ ($i=1,2$) are the face sheet extensional, coupling and bending stiffnesses.

The small deformation strain-displacement relations read:

FLAT FACE LAMINATES

$$u_i = u_{0i} + z\beta_i, \quad \varepsilon_i = \varepsilon_{0i} + z\kappa_i, \quad \varepsilon_{0i} = u_{0i,x}, \quad \beta_i = -w_{i,x}, \quad \kappa_i = \beta_{i,x}, \quad i = 1,2 \quad (4)$$

CURVED FACE LAMINATES

$$u_i = u_{0i} + z\beta_i, \quad \varepsilon_i = \varepsilon_{0i} + z\kappa_i, \quad \varepsilon_{0i} = \frac{u_{0i,\theta} + w_i}{R_i}, \quad \beta_i = \frac{u_{0i} - w_{i,\theta}}{R_i}, \quad \kappa_i = \frac{\beta_{i,\theta}}{R_i}, \quad i = 1,2$$

(5)

where β_i represent the rotations, and R_i is the curvature of the face mid-line.

With reference to Fig. 3, the equilibrium equations for the flat and curved sandwich panels can be expressed in the form:

FLAT SANDWICH PANELS

$$\begin{aligned} N_{1,x} + (n_1 - \tau_c) &= 0, & Q_{1,x} + (q_1 - \sigma_c^t) &= 0, & M_{1,x} - Q_1 + \frac{f_1}{2}\tau_c - m_1 &= 0 \\ N_{2,x} + (n_2 + \tau_c) &= 0, & Q_{2,x} + (q_2 + \sigma_c^b) &= 0, & M_{2,x} - Q_2 + \frac{f_2}{2}\tau_c - m_2 &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

CURVED SANDWICH PANELS

$$\begin{aligned}
 N_{1,\theta} + Q_1 + R_1 n_1 - R_c^t \tau_c^t &= 0, & Q_{1,\theta} - N_1 + R_1 q_1 - R_c^t \sigma_c^t &= 0 \\
 M_{1,\theta} - R_1 Q_1 + R_c^t \frac{f_1}{2} \tau_c^t - R_1 m_1 &= 0 \\
 N_{2,\theta} + Q_2 + R_2 n_2 + R_c^b \tau_c^b &= 0, & Q_{2,\theta} - N_2 + R_2 q_2 + R_c^b \sigma_c^b &= 0 \\
 M_{2,\theta} - R_2 Q_2 + R_c^b \frac{f_2}{2} \tau_c^b - R_2 m_2 &= 0
 \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

Figure 3. Equilibrium elements for flat and curved sandwich panels.

where n_i , q_i and m_i ($i=1,2$) are distributed in-plane, lateral and bending moment loads. Superscripts “ t ”/“ b ” refer to the “top”/“bottom” core/face boundaries, respectively.

Combination of the face sheet equations, Eqs. (3)-(7), with the core layer equations, Eqs. (1)-(2), and by imposing continuity of the displacements across the core/face boundaries, the set of governing differential equations is obtained. The governing equations has the same principal form in the flat and the curved sections:

$$\frac{d}{ds} \{y(s)\} = [A(s)]\{y(s)\} + \{B(s)\} \quad (8)$$

$$\{y(s)\} = \{u_{01}, w_1, \beta_1, N_1, M_1, Q_1, \tau_c, \tau_{c,s}, u_{02}, w_2, \beta_2, N_2, M_2, Q_2\}$$

where $\{y(s)\}$ is the vector for fundamental variables, $[A(s)]$ is a stiffness matrix, and $\{B(s)\}$ is a vector of non-homogeneous load terms.

Specification of boundary conditions, external loads and numerical solution

BOUNDARY CONDITIONS

The boundary conditions prescribed for the ship hull CS shown in Fig. 1 are:

“Deck” – $s=0$: “Clamping conditions”.

Junctions between vertical and curved sections: Continuity of fundamental variables.

“Keel” - vertical symmetry plane: The triangular “keel” section shown in Fig. 1 is approximated as a rigid body, and “zero” total vertical stress resultant, “zero” horizontal displacements and “zero” rotations are enforced in the faces and core of the bottom sandwich panel.

EXTERNAL LOADS

For the purposes of the present study, only hydraulic head loading (p_h) and simplified vertically symmetric “blast” loading (p_b) conditions are assumed:

$$p(s) = p_h + p_b \quad (9)$$

$$p_h = p_h(z) = g\rho z \quad \text{and} \quad p_b = \text{constant}$$

where ρ is the density of water ($1,000 \text{ kg/m}^3$), g is the gravitational constant (9.82 m/s^2) and z is the vertical distance below the waterline. Both load types act below water level, see Fig. 1:

NUMERICAL SOLUTION

The governing equations together with the boundary conditions constitute a boundary value problem, which is solved numerically using the “multi-segment method of integration”, also known as the “multiple point shooting method” described in for instance [14], and used recently in [11-13].

NUMERICAL STUDY

The overall geometric dimensions of the hull CS are specified in accordance with a recent ONR technology demonstration program. The material properties and the face and core thicknesses are chosen within the range known from typical naval applications in Scandinavia over the last two decades (e.g. the Standard Flex 300 multipurpose vessels of the Royal Danish Navy for instance).

Material Properties (defined in cross section plane)

The constituent materials are assumed to be quasi-isotropic glas/vinylester for the faces, and cross-linked PVC foam core with the following mechanical properties:

Foam core: $E_c=300$ MPa, $G_c=90$ MPa (Divinycell, density 200 kg/m³).
 Face laminates: $E_f=20.0$ GPa, $\nu_f=0.3$.

Geometry

With reference to Fig.1 the hull section CS is defined by:

CS height: $H= 3,277$ mm (129'')
 CS half width: $W/2= 2972$ mm (117'')
 Angle \square : 80°
 Deck to waterline distance: $S_W=1,100$ mm
 Waterline to curved section distance: $S_1=200$ mm

Face thicknesses: $f_1=f_2=5.0$ mm.

Core thickness: $c=100$ mm.

The remaining quantities appearing in Fig.1 can be calculated from the above.

Loading

As described before, the loading is given by Eqs. (9) corresponding to hydraulic head and blast loads. In accordance with the ONR technology demonstration program quoted above, the underwater "blast" load is assumed to be equivalent with a static load of $p_b=4000$ psf= 28 psi= 0.193 MPa.

Numerical results

Figure 4. Idealized ship hull CS subjected to hydraulic head and underwater blast loads in undeformed and deformed (magnification of deflections=5) configurations.

DEFORMATIONS

Fig.4 shows the ship hull CS in undeformed and deformed configurations under the combined action of hydraulic head and blast loading. The undeformed CS (inner and outer skin) is shown dimensionally correct, whereas the deflections on which the deformed CS is based have been magnified by a factor of 5. In reality, the peak lateral deflection is about 179 mm (flat bottom panel), and the peak in-plane deflection is about -50 mm (curved panel – inner skin).

SHEAR RESULTANT DISTRIBUTION

Fig. 5 shows the distribution of shear stress resultants in the ship hull CS. The waterline is positioned at $s=1,100$ mm, and all loads are applied below this level. It is seen that the core is responsible for the majority of the shear load transfer, except adjacent to the “keel” where Q_1 and Q_2 reach considerable magnitudes, thus signifying that severe localized bending effects are present at this location. It is further seen that shear peaks of considerable magnitude are present at 3 distinct locations: The junctions between the flat and the curved sections, and at the position of the “keel”. The latter is a consequence of the very restrictive boundary conditions imposed at the vertical plane of symmetry of the CS.

Figure 5. Distribution of transverse shear stress resultants in ship hull CS.

CORE STRESSES

Fig. 6 shows the distribution of the stresses in the core material. As indicated in Fig. 5, it is observed that considerable shear stress peaks (σ_c^b =inner face/core boundary; σ_c^t =outer face/core boundary) are present at the junctions between the curved and the flat panels, as well as in the vicinity of the “keel”. The most severe peaks are located near the “keel” due to the restrictive boundary conditions imposed here. This is also revealed by the transverse normal stress distribution (σ_c^b =inner face/core boundary; σ_c^t =outer face/core boundary) displayed in Fig. 5. Thus, the transverse normal stresses are of insignificant magnitude except in the close vicinity of the “keel” where very large compressive stresses are induced.

Figure 6. Distribution of core shear and transverse normal stresses in ship hull CS.

Figure 7. Distribution of face normal stresses in ship hull CS.

FACE STRESSES

Finally, Fig. 7 shows the distribution of the normal stresses in the inner and outer fibers of the faces of the ship hull CS. Significant “global” bending moments of opposite signs are seen to be present in the curved and bottom sandwich panels (primarily caused by the blast loading p_b). These bending effects are accompanied by high in-plane compressive membrane stresses. The combined effect is that one face is loaded very lightly, whereas the other face is subjected to significant compressive stresses. In addition to these “global” effects, caused by the hydrostatic pressure loading, very high stress peaks are induced in the vicinity of the “keel”, thus again showing the severity of the boundary conditions present at the vertical plane of symmetry of the ship hull CS.

CONCLUSIONS

Preliminary results regarding the design of sandwich ship hulls using composite sandwich construction has been shown. The analysis is restricted to considering a 2-D cross section of a ship hull subjected to the extreme case of hydraulic head and blast loading acting simultaneously. The analysis has been carried out using a high-order sandwich theory formulation in which the elastic response of each face is accounted for individually, including bending-stretching coupling. The core material is modeled as a special type of orthotropic solid possessing stiffness only in the through-thickness direction. Consequently, the model includes the transverse flexibility of the core material, and the sandwich panel thickness can change during deformation.

A sandwich ship hull cross section corresponding to a recent ONR technology demonstration program has provided the basis for a numerical study. The results reveal that significant bending and shearing actions are present under the extreme loadings considered. Severe shear stress peaks are induced in the core material, and severe predominantly compressive normal stresses are induced in the faces. Thus, core shear failure and/or buckling failure of the faces are likely modes of failure under the load conditions considered. In addition to the “global” shearing and bending actions, severe stress concentrations are induced in the vicinity of the “keel” of the hull. This is caused by the restrictive boundary conditions that are effectively exerted at the vertical plane of symmetry of the hull, and caution is required in the design to avoid premature structural failure at this location.

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